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Nosebleed

You try to speak a sentence nice and loud,
"Ahem." You clear your throat and face a formal crowd.
But grammar breaks, "the the the..." the twisted English slips,
And "trying hard" just trips and twists upon your lips.

An urgent email from a foreign client waits for a reply,
You stare at your reply "Drafts" and heave a heavy sigh.
How do you start? "Good day," "Good morning," "Hello,"
or "Dear respect"?
You freeze in place, unsure now what to expect.

Went to a grocery store and checked a product label on the shelf,
Reading... and trying to guess the words to calm yourself.
After 10 long years, you buy the box, though clueless about what it's
for,
You say, "Because you must," and walk out, still unsure.

A group of foreigners stops to ask you for the way,
You look them in the eye, you panic, thinking what on earth to say.
You try to build sentences, "There! No! Yes! Outside!", short and clear,
But you drop the verbs and the rest, you freeze in fear.

You call a hotline just to ask a price,
The agent speaks in English, crisp and nice.
You try to match their accent and their tone,
But butcher every sentence into static on the phone.

You ride the jeep, and a foreigner asks you to pass his fare,
"Keep the change!" you shout into the air.
But English slips, you fumble with the phrase, and not your money in
the first place,
"His. His money," you tell, lost in a stuttered, awkward, humid haze.

In a club, you stand before a sign with glowing light,

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The instructions are in English, clear, bold, and bright.
You squint and nod and guess what the words might mean,
Confused by the letters, a blur you've only barely seen.

In a classroom, an essay looms, a blank and silent page,
You feel a quiet, simmering rage.
To your teacher, "Can I write in my mother tongue?", you wish to plead,
But pride and rules forbid the help you need.

You meet an AFAM, dreaming of the day,
He walks through your front door to finally stay.
But when he speaks, "hey!", your courage starts to fail,
You are trapped inside a language, thin and frail.

Without a choice, you try to make a point, to speak your mind,
But after trying, you leave the truest words behind.
You mentally search for words that instantly vanish into thin,
Sad! You are caught in a war; you cannot hope to win.

So through the strain, you strive to hold the lead,
And try to hide the mental sharp *nosebleed*.